

components were observed for pathways and crosses \times pathways interactions, suggesting that environment had a minimal effect on the comparative yielding ability of the two crosses.

Because only two crosses were studied, these results are not conclusive. But it appears probable that there are no advantages in early generation selection under dryland conditions. Consid-

ering the many operational advantages, dryland rice breeders should consider growing all early generation materials under wetland conditions. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Adverse soils tolerance

Identification of iron toxicity in Brazil

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Symptoms similar to those of iron toxicity have been observed in rice-producing regions of Santa Catarina State, Brazil. In 1977, their cause was studied for the first time.

Many brownish spots appeared on the tips of older leaves of affected plants

and later spread to the basal parts. The leaves (except the midrib) turned brown and dried. In many areas the brown color turned reddish. The roots were dark brown and were damaged. All the symptoms were observed at the maximum tillering stage.

At the panicle initiation stage and at maturity, samples of roots, culms, and leaves were collected from a rice farmer's field at Camboriú, Itajaí River Valley. Simultaneously plant samples were collected from another plot where

no symptoms were observed. The samples were sent to different laboratories for analysis of the contents of nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, iron, and manganese. One laboratory replicated the sample analysis twice.

The results were compared with those found for various elements by Tanaka and Yoshida in 1970. The iron content of the affected leaves at maturity averaged 846 ppm. Iron toxicity was confirmed as the cause of the symptoms. ■

A mass-screening method for salt tolerance of rice varieties at seedling stage

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Rice varieties at the seedling stage were screened for salt tolerance in the greenhouse at RRS in Chinsurah.

The experiment was designed to investigate the effects of salinity on seedling growth (up to 21 days) of 100 rice varieties — including the standard variety SR26 B — under 17.5 mmho/cm of saline water (see figure). The salt solution was prepared by adding sodium chloride to distilled water. Normal and saline water were maintained at a suitable level in sterilized cylindrical, glass jars (9.5 cm \times 5.0 cm). Salt solution was estimated by determining electrical conductivity in mmho/cm at 25° C of the solution.

Blotting paper rolls were inserted in the glass jars. Two sets of jars, one for each treatment (normal and saline water), were placed side by side. Five seeds of each variety were made to adhere to the blotting paper by means of their seed hairs so the embryos

Germination and seedling growth of the same variety in saline water (left) and fresh water (right).

remained submerged.

Each variety was allowed to germinate in the culture jars. Water, i.e. fresh and saline, was added to the jars and maintained to a depth of 7.0 cm. The salt solution was adjusted to the desired

concentration at weekly intervals. The salt tolerance of each variety at seedling stage was determined by length, fresh weight, dry weight, and water content of root and shoot.

A high concentration of saline water delayed germination and depressed seedling growth for all varieties. General effects of salinity were darkening of the green color, withering of leaf tips, followed by yellowing and drying. A high degree of salinity significantly reduced the length of the root and shoot of the rice seedlings. Root growth was more depressed than was shoot growth.

Marked varietal differences in salt tolerance were observed (see table). Hamilton (selected from Nonabokra), a newly recommended variety, showed the best root growth. Root length development in BPI 76 was poor. Hamilton and Dholabokra had significantly higher values for shoot length than the other varieties. The adverse effect of salinity on shoot length was most pronounced in BPI 76.

Fresh weight and dry matter production of root and shoot also were depressed by salinity. Hamilton gave higher values for fresh weight and water content of root and shoot. But Dheral and Marichsail proved better in shoot